

India: A Promising New Power in the Global Arena

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Abstract: As India enters her 76th year of independence, the relative volatility of the international landscape, in addition to the starkly different challenges in the contemporary context, has led to increased opportunities for her, as a prospective global player. This article, therefore, seeks to delve into the broader shades of perspectives on the prospective road ahead regarding India's foreign policy objectives, not only in the present scenario but also in the next 25 years or so, marking its centenary of sovereignty.

Bottom-line-up-front: India stands at a crucial juncture in shaping its foreign policy objectives amidst global dynamics, presenting both challenges and opportunities as it journeys towards its centenary of sovereignty in the next 25 years.

Problem statement: How can India navigate the evolving international landscape and position itself as a significant global player while addressing the challenges and opportunities?

So what?: Strategic planning and proactive decision-making by Indian policymakers, in collaboration with key international partners, are essential to chart a successful foreign policy course for India leading up to its centenary of sovereignty.

Lacking Consensus and Neglected Dialogue

The decline of U.S. hegemony and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has created a strained, more competitive world. [India seeks to draw nations together, avoid the building of competing power blocs, and foster healthy dialogue between powers, great and small.](#)

India became independent from the British Empire 76 years ago, on August 15, 1947. The world has changed since then. U.S. dominance is waning, and the international community is in a volatile state. This creates opportunities for a prospective global player like India.

Yet, the road to the global spotlight for New Delhi may be difficult. The Russia–Ukraine War, the Taliban takeover of Afghanistan and the growing economic concerns of India’s South Asian neighbours, [Sri Lanka and Pakistan](#), which, despite the same, continually pressurize India at the diplomatic level, all hinder India’s place in international affairs.

These adversities demonstrate the lack of consensus and the sheer neglect of dialogue and diplomacy in the international community. In the words of Samir Saran, the President of the renowned Observer Research Foundation (ORF), “When the pandemic first broke out there was a rise in protectionist sentiments and countries scrambled to protect their citizens and close off borders.”

India’s foreign policy may be characterized as realpolitik, but it is also a blend of both pragmatism and morality. Its job in this decade is to navigate the now post-COVID environment to pursue its interests and to foster a sense of collegiality among nations.

Strategic Multilateralism in the Indo-Pacific

Writing for the think tank Gateway House, Indian Ambassador Rajiv Bhatia raised a fundamental question: Is India a middle, great, or in-between power? That is a question that is currently still being decided as India finds its place in the world. However, the uncertainty means that India, committed to multilateralism, will have to balance its focus on its neighbours with its focus on the great powers.

India seeks to actively engage in regional dialogue by participating in several multilateral fora like the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (India, Australia, Japan and the U.S.), BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, the People's Republic of China [PRC] and South Africa), the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO, which includes PRC, Russia, Iran and most of Central Asia), and, of course, the G20. Through these organizations, India tries to lead by example and encourage partnership between all nations on equal terms, opposing the PRC's attempts to exclude the West and establish hegemony in the East.

Similarly, India has revived and expanded its "Look East Policy," strengthening trade ties with its neighbours in Southeast Asia. Leaders from India and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) declared 2022 the "ASEAN-India Friendship Year," marking 30 years of relations.

Central to the Indian foreign policy has been a larger focus on developmental and economic issues. Writing for *The Diplomat*, Raymond E. Vickery, Jr. points out that India's priorities at the SCO were three "pillars of cooperation," or startups, science and technology, and traditional medicine.

India's domestic circumstances, such as enhanced infrastructural growth as a result of the [Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure \(CDRI\)](#), (a mechanism, aimed at promoting systematic and sustainable development). Proliferation of [multilateral development banks](#), a vibrant private sector and academic heft. Institutions have given impetus to its leadership initiatives. However, this has also imposed additional responsibility to work actively with the international community in line with its larger objectives of "One Earth, One Family, One Future." This can be done through a consensus on both political and apolitical issues, as seen in initiatives of vaccine diplomacy during the COVID-19 pandemic. In supporting faster, sustainable and inclusive growth by highlighting international support for diverse social and economic sectors, India can impact the most vulnerable and disadvantaged.

As the world's largest democracy, the third-largest economy in terms of purchasing power parity, and the second-most populous country, India will undeniably be a central pole as the international community continues to develop.

India's Rising Global Acceptance and Credibility

As a complex and diverse country, [India has the potential to become a global leader](#) in various fields due to its large population, rapidly growing economy, and rich cultural heritage. However, the acceptance of India as a global leader will depend on several factors, including how it positions itself on the world stage, its foreign policy approach, economic reforms, and its ability to address domestic challenges effectively.

In terms of global acceptance, [India](#) has made significant strides in recent years by playing a more active role in international forums such as the G20, BRICS, and various United Nations bodies. [Its contributions to peacekeeping missions](#), climate change initiatives, and economic cooperation have been recognized by the international community. [India's soft power](#), including its vibrant film industry, music, cuisine, and traditional practices like yoga, have also helped improve its global image.

Regionally, India's leadership ambitions may face challenges due to historical conflicts and geopolitical rivalries with neighbouring countries like [Pakistan](#) and [PRC](#). India's approach towards resolving border disputes, fostering economic cooperation, and promoting regional stability will be crucial in gaining acceptance as a regional leader. Building strong diplomatic relationships with neighbouring countries and promoting regional peace and prosperity will be key factors in this regard.

While it is important for India to aspire for leadership roles on the global and regional stage, it is equally important for it to earn the respect and acceptance of other countries through its actions and policies. [By demonstrating a commitment to democratic values, promoting economic growth](#), engaging in multilateral cooperation, and addressing social and environmental challenges, India can enhance its credibility as a responsible global leader. Ultimately, the acceptance of India as a global leader will depend on its ability to balance its national interests with its commitment to global cooperation, respect for diversity, and promotion of peace and prosperity on a global scale.

[It will require consistent efforts to build trust, foster dialogue](#), and work towards common goals with other countries and international organizations. It falls upon India to assert her demands more vocally as a key international player and potential global superpower for its own sake and the sake of the broader developing world.

Challenges and the Way Forward

Despite India's strategic positioning, the exercise of international leadership won't be easy. The actions of India's long-standing ally, Russia, and its regional competitor, the PRC, in the context of the Russia–Ukraine War marked a return to Cold War politics. As gaps continue to open between the East and the West, India will struggle as it tries to draw the two worlds together.

India's role within the Global South is pivotal, representing the interests and concerns of developing countries on the global stage. Economically, India advocates for fair trade practices, technology transfer, and inclusive growth opportunities for all nations within the Global South. India actively promotes South-South cooperation to foster mutual development and overcome common challenges faced by developing nations.

In the context of climate change, India emphasizes the principles of climate justice and calls for developed countries to take greater responsibility for mitigating the impacts of global warming. India highlights the need for financial and technological support to enable developing countries to transition to sustainable, low-carbon economies and adapt to the effects of climate change.

On the diplomatic front, India advocates for reforming international institutions like the United Nations to give voice to the perspectives and concerns of countries in the Global South. Through active participation in platforms such as the Non-Aligned Movement and regional organizations like SAARC, India strengthens political ties and promotes cooperation among developing nations in addressing common challenges.

Regarding human rights, India adopts a nuanced approach that seeks to uphold fundamental rights and freedoms while respecting the cultural diversity and sovereign rights of nations within the Global South. India emphasizes the need for a more inclusive and context-sensitive approach to human rights that considers each country's unique circumstances.

Overall, India's engagement with the Global South reflects its commitment to promoting a fairer and more equitable global order where solidarity, cooperation, and mutual respect among developing nations are central in shaping international policies and initiatives. India's multifaceted approach across economic, environmental, political, and human rights domains underscores its aspiration to be a leading voice for the Global South and drive positive change on the world stage.

As the nation embarks upon a new journey, the global challenges do not seem to lessen; neither must India's commitment to dialogue, international consensus, and harmony be slacken.